

Pword-report

Language name: **Chrau (LID 1139)**
Name: Thomas Goldammer
Sources: David D. Thomas (1971) *Chrau Grammar*. University of Hawai'i Press.
Internet version of *The Ethnologue*, Vol. 15 (2005). www.ethnologue.com.
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I Language profile

of spks: 22'500 (in 1999, census)
place: Dông Nai, Tayninh, Binhlong provinces (Vietnam)
Contact lgs.: Vietnamese
Status: no official language
Prospects: only some parents speak Chrau to their children; endangered, but 30% are literate in Chrau
Struct. results: no information

General note:

- the orthography is sometimes misleading, for example: *q* [ʔ], *s/c* [ɕ], *v* [b], *b* [ʔb], *đ* [ʔd], *ch* [c], *chh* [c^h]
- diacritics on vowels do not mark tone or stress, they are only used to mark length and vowel quality

II Morpheme types

1. _____ Stem

2. _____ Restricted preposed formative

tăm 'RECP' only attached to verbs, immediately preceding them

- | | | | | | | | | |
|-----|-------------------------|------------|-----------|-----|------------------------------------|------------|------------|------------|
| (1) | <i>vơn</i> | <i>tăm</i> | <i>ôp</i> | (2) | <i>vơn</i> | <i>tăm</i> | <i>dip</i> | <i>măt</i> |
| | we.incl | RECP | work | | we.incl | RECP | look | eye |
| | 'we will work together' | | | | 'we looked into each other's eyes' | | | |

3. _____ Restricted postposed formative

iưn 'DAT' only attached to NPs, immediately following them
de/je 'GEN' dito (for examples see section VII below, ex. (28-32))

- | | | | | | |
|-----|-----------------------|-----------|------------|------------|------------|
| (3) | <i>ăn</i> | <i>ôp</i> | <i>răm</i> | <i>nẻh</i> | <i>iưn</i> |
| | I | work | field | he | DAT |
| | 'I make him a field.' | | | | |

4. _____ Restricted infix

-an- 'NMLZ' not productive but many examples, only attached to verbs, result is N, A or CLF

- | | | |
|-----|----------------------|------------------------------------|
| (4) | <i>păt</i> 'squeeze' | → <i>panăt</i> 'handful' (CLF) |
| | <i>gon</i> 'hunt' | → <i>ganon</i> 'hunting blind' (N) |
| | <i>vỏh</i> 'know' | → <i>vanỏh</i> 'wise' (A) |

III Syllable

Syllable structure

Analysis by D. Thomas (1971):

Two types of syllables: main syllables with pattern (C₁)(C₂)C₃V(C₄), and presyllables with pattern C_pV.

- C₁ can only be a nasal, which is homorganic to following consonants, or if it is not homorganic, a presyllable has to be there. The nasal can be long or short.
- C₂ can be any obstruent or glottal consonant
- C₃ can be /l r w j/.

- Note that David Thomas (1971) analyzed aspirated stops as a series of stop + /h/, which does not fit to the syllable pattern given in his grammar, since initial clusters like *mphl* are attested.
- V can be every vowel, long or short, or a diphthong, but in open syllables neither short vowels nor diphthongs occur.
- C₄ can be /p, t, c, k, ʔ, ɕ, h, m, n, ɲ, l, r, w, j/ or the cluster /kh/
- The presyllable can have /p, t, c, k, ʔ, b, d, ʝ, g, m, l~r, ɕ, (h), (w), (j)/ as onset (C_p). /h w j/ occur very rarely, /l/ and /r/ are not fully contrastive in this position. Also the contrast between voiced and voiceless stops is not clear, there is some free variation among the words having stop or liquid onset in the presyllable (*pataw* ~ *vataw* [p ~ b] 'king', *lapũng* ~ *rapũng* [l ~ r] 'melon', but: *panang* 'room' vs. *vanãng* 'night', *lawa* 'a fish' vs. *rawa* 'spread around').
- The vowel of the presyllable is /ə/ which surfaces as [i u i ə] depending on the surrounding consonants. This vowel is shorter than a short vowel in the main syllable, and even more short if the cluster of the main syllable starts with a nasal. /ɽ/ is also possible in this position

→ This analysis is problematic not only concerning aspiration but also concerning the homorganic nasal rule and the possible nasal length. Another problem is /kh/ which would be the only cluster attested in presyllable onsets after D.T.'s analysis.

Possible main syllable onset clusters after D. Thomas: (those in () brackets are rarely attested, those in [] only occur in Vietnamese loans)

- pl, pr, pj, ph,
- tr, tw, th,
- cr, cj, cw, ch,
- kl, kr, kj, kw, kh,
- ʔl, (ʔr), ʔj, ʔw,
- ʔbl, (ʔbr), (ʔbj),
- [ʔdw],
- bl, br, bj, bw,
- (dl), dr,
- jr, j, jw,
- gl, gr, gj, gw,
- (ɕj), ɕw,
- hl, (hr), hj, hw,
- ml, mr, mw, mh, mʔb, mb, mp, (mt),
- nl, nr, nj, nw, nh, nʔd, nd, nt, (nb),
- nr, nh, nj, nc, nɕ,
- ɲl, ɲr, (ɲj), (ɲw), ɲg, ɲk, (ɲs), (ɲt)
- phl, phw, phj, chw, khl, khw, khj, mph, mpr, mʔbl, mbl, mbr, mhl, nth, ntr, nʔdw, ndr, nhl, nhw, nhj, njch, njr, njh, njk, njkw, njgl, njgr, mphl

My analysis of the main syllable onset and the presyllable structure:

Two types of syllables: main syllables with pattern (C₁)C₂V(C₃), and presyllables with pattern (C₄)V(C₅)

- C₁ can be any obstruent, nasal or glottal consonant
- C₂ can be /l r w j/
- C₃ and C₄ are the same as C₄ and C_p, respectively, in D. Thomas' analysis, with the exception that not /kh/ but /k^h/ is allowed in the onset of presyllables.
- The nucleus of a presyllable can be either a reduced vowel, a nasal or /ɽ/. If it is a nasal, this nasal is homorganic to the following consonant.
- C₅ can only be a nasal.

In my analysis, the possible onset clusters of the main syllable would be:

- pl, pr, pj,
- p^hl, p^hw, p^hj,
- tr, tw,
- cr, cj, cw,
- c^hw,
- kl, kr, kj, kw,
- k^hl, k^hw, k^hj,
- ʔl, ʔr, ʔj, ʔw,
- ʔbl, ʔbr, ʔbj,

- ʔdw,
- bl, br, bj, bw,
- dl, dr,
- jr, jj, jw,
- gl, gr, gj, gw,
- ɕj, ɕw,
- hl, hr, hj, hw,
- ml, mr, mw,
- nl, nr, nj, nw,
- jr, rj,
- ɲl, ɲr, ɲj, ɲw

→ thus every obstruent or nasal or glottal consonant + liquid/approximant

Examples (IPA transcription of examples is not given in the grammar, but the writing system is described using IPA):

- | | | | | | |
|------|--------------------------|-----------|------|---------------------------|-------------|
| (5) | <i>ndăh</i> [ŋ.dăh] | ‘not yet’ | (6) | <i>camlăh</i> [cəm.lăh] | ‘deny’ |
| (7) | <i>nsyěq</i> [ŋ.ɕjěʔ] | ‘cough’ | (8) | <i>glu</i> [glu:] | ‘leech’ |
| (9) | <i>hwi</i> [hwi:] | ‘wide’ | (10) | <i>mprăng</i> [m.pɾăŋ] | ‘run’ |
| (11) | <i>mvlôr</i> [m.blɔːɾ] | ‘toss up’ | (12) | <i>candăl</i> [căn.ʔda:l] | ‘middle’ |
| (13) | <i>khlang</i> [kʰlaːŋ] | ‘eagle’ | (14) | <i>khamay</i> [kʰəmaːj] | ‘you (pl.)’ |
| (15) | <i>prhwa</i> [pɾ.hwa:] | ‘pulled’ | (16) | <i>vrwanh</i> [bɾ.waːɲ] | ‘striped’ |
| (17) | <i>kammlo</i> [kəm.mlɔː] | ‘dumb’ | (18) | <i>gut</i> [gɿt] | ‘know’ |

Monomoraic words

There are no monomoraic words, since short vowels only occur in closed syllables and presyllables.

Vowel-initial words

No information in the grammar whether or not onsetless main syllables are allowed. There are words like *nniêt* [...ŋ.ɲjeʔ] ‘lazy’, where there is no information whether or not the presyllable has a glottal stop onset. Additionally, there are words like *ănh* [...ăjɲ] ‘1’ or *u* [...u:] ‘in, at’, *alăc* ‘wine’. Note, that phonemic glottal stop is written *q*, as in *qua* [ʔuɔ] ‘very’.

Polysyllabic morphemes

Lexical morphemes and pronouns, as *panang* ‘room’, *khamay* ‘you.PL’ can have up to two syllables, a presyllable and a main syllable. Function words are always monosyllabic.

Phonotactics

cf. syllable restrictions,

Additionally, back vowels are barred before /w/, front vowels before /j/.

Superheavy syllables

Superheavy syllables can occur, cf. examples (10-15) above.

IV Tone & Stress

Tone

There is no distinctive lexical tone, but some (mostly function) words bear high or low tone. For example question words, negation words and intensifiers, as well as numerals and some particles have a high tone, but if there are more than one such word, only the first one keeps its high tone.

(19) *ăn* *éq* *v**l**a**m* *si-ur* *mai*
 M H M M RF
 I not meet wife you
 'I haven't met your wife.' (note: *si-ur* is a compound consisting of two pwords)

(20) *saq* *éq* *g**ě**h* *du* *l**â**m* *g**õ**ng*
 M H M M(!) M RF
 go not get one CLF? meat
 '...went not getting a single bit of meat'

Low tone words: Sentence-final particles, some conjunctions have a low tone. Also a subject pronoun which is shifted to the right edge of the sentence, gets low tone:

(21) *saq* *â**m*
 M L
 go AFF
 'Yes, let's go.'

(22) *ăn* *g**â**m* *n**ě**h*
 M L M
 I and he
 'I and he'

(23) *saq* *nggô* *v**ơ**n*
 M M L
 go hunt we.incl
 'Let's go hunting.'

Stress

Word stress is always on the last syllable, thus on the main syllable. Presyllables cannot bear stress.

V Other Non-concatenative Processes

Ablaut

Nothing found.

List of all phonological processes

1. Coda neutralization
 /p t c k/ → [-released] / ____)_{σ/φ/ω}

(In presyllable codas stop phonemes cannot occur, thus it remains unclear whether the domain of this rule is the syllable or the foot or pword.)

(24) *krwat* [kʰwaʔ] 'necktie'

2. Glide insertion
 Ø → [j] / V____c, ʝ, ɲ, ɕ)_σ (domain = φ/ω, because the rule only applies in mainsyllables)

(25) *ăn* [ǎjɲ] 'I'

VI "Free" Grammatical Morphemes
VII Polymorphemic Stem forms

Nearly all grammatical markers seem to be free pwords. Exceptions are the high tone directional prepositions *tu* 'to', *a* 'from, at', *u* 'in, at' and the low tone particle *ca* 'like'. They are attached to following monosyllabic words as presyllable but remain free pwords before disyllabics (no example found).

- (26) *mai panh ca=nỏq*
 you.sg talk like-DEM.DIST
 'You talk like that.'
- (27) *chẻq ảnh vữq u=heq*
 let I sleep in-DEM.PROX
 'Let me sleep here.'

A marker with a special variation is the GEN marker *de ~ je / ảnh___* (after personal pronoun *ảnh* '1s' the marker changes to *je*, there is said to be no change with other words ending in *nh* [ɲ]) (but no example given in the grammar). The marker is obligatory when the clause is a statement of possession (cf. (28)), and/or when the head noun of a genitive complex is missing (as in (28) or (30)). The marker can be used to mark the identification with an action (for emphasizing the agent) (31). It can also mark the experiencer of an action (32).

- (28) *iẻr heq ảnh je*
 chicken DEM I GEN
 'This chicken is mine.'
- (29) *iẻr patau de*
 chicken king GEN
 'the king's chicken'
- (30) *camvu de iẻr heq*
 who GEN chicken DEM
 'Whose is this chicken?'
- (31) *ảnh khủn iẻr, ảnh je*
 I steal chicken I GEN
 'I was it who steals chickens.'
- (32) *vu pảh ảnh je*
 someone hit I GEN
 'Someone hit me.'

VIII Compounds, Concatenations, Juxtapositions

Compounds occur, but the parts keep their status as pwords:

- (33) *si-ur* 'wife'
chhỏ-rapaq 'guava tree'
ca-co 'catfish'

IX Reduplication

There are three types of reduplication. All of them show the same phonological pattern, thus the two reduplicants are different pwords.

1. _____ Simple reduplication

The reduplicants are not free forms. It is lexical and obligatorily:

- (34) *praq praq* 'monkeys chattering' (*praq)
klɔ klɔ 'darkly, unclear' (*klɔ)

2. _____ Alternating reduplication

The first member may be a free form. The alternation is unpredictable.

- (35) changing onset: *phung lung* 'heavy falling'
choc mloc 'only, alone'
 (36) changing vowel: *mêp map* 'look diligently'
 (37) more complex changes: *mbăq mban* 'unskillfully'
rawênh rawai 'dizzy'
 (38) redupl. of a compound: *tong-ke? tong-ke* 'curved handle'

3. _____ Additive reduplication

Between the two reduplicants, an additional presyllable is added (either *ŋ-*, *si-*, *la-*, or *ra-*). The first or the (extended) second member can occur as free lexems (marked by ^(x)).

- (39) *blăp m-blăp* 'scratching'
vôq^(x) m-vôq 'going directly'
kruq si-kruq 'frantically, vigorously'
wênh ra-wênh^(x) 'winding around'
pôc^(x) la-pôc 'chopping a tree'

X Phrase/Sentence-level phenomena

The clause intonation is level mid with a rise-fall or a rise at the end (declaratives). The clause-final rise occurs if the last syllable has a short vowel and a voiceless coda. Otherwise the rise-fall occurs.

- (40) *mai hôm gûq u=nốq*
 M M M M **R**
 you.sg still live in=DEM.DIST
 'You still live there.'
- (41) *saq éq gẻh du lâm gống*
 M H M M M **RF**
 go not get one CLF? meat
 '...went not getting a single bit of meat'

Questions can be optionally marked by a low tone final particle *be*, which results in a fall-rise tone shape at the end:

- (42) *mai gut ôp be?*
 M M M **FR**
 you.sg know lumber Q
 'Do you know how to lumber?'

Focus questions have a rising tone:

- (43) *nhi?*
R
 'Do you really mean "nhi"?'

Instructions are often followed by the attention getting particle *σ* which has either rising or falling tone. The regular answer to such an instruction is *σ!* with a falling tone:

(44)	<i>mai</i>	<i>sĩq,</i>	<i>ơ!</i>	<i>ơ!</i>
	M	R	F	F
	you.sg	go.home	!	!
	^You go home, hear!		'OK!'	

XI Other Special things

- Geminates: only attested heterosyllabically with a syllabic nasal or nasal coda in the presyllable followed by a nasal onset in the main syllable: *nniêt* 'lazy', *kammlo* 'dumb'
- Foot: seems to be iambic since stress is word-final and a word can maximally consist of two syllables which could form a foot. Thus every pword is a single foot.